

Book of Abstract

ICCOM 2025

*1st International Conference on Communication
and Digital Multimedia*

TOWARD AN IMPACTFUL DIGITAL
MULTIMEDIA ECOSYSTEM:
INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY,
LITERACY, AND GOVERNANCE

NOVEMBER 19, 2025

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CONFERENCE PROGRAM

SEKOLAH TINGGI MULTI MEDIA

JL. MAGELANG KM 6 YOGYAKARTA, INDONESIA

Conference Program

1st International Conference on Communication and Digital Multimedia (ICCDM) 2025

Theme: Toward an Impactful Digital Multimedia Ecosystem: Innovation, Technology, Literacy, and Governance

Venue: Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media (STMM), Yogyakarta, Indonesia (Hybrid Format),
Date: November 19, 2025, Time Zone: UTC+7

Time	Agenda	Speaker / Notes	PIC
08:00 – 08:50	Registration, Coffee & Networking	Registration desk opens, participants arrival, morning refreshment & networking	Registration Team
08:50 – 09:00	Opening and Introduction by Host	Short greeting and overview by host	Master of Ceremonies
09:00 – 09:10	Opening Performance	Cultural performance by STMM students (Student Video Screening)	Art & Culture Division
09:10 – 09:15	National Anthem	Singing of Indonesia Raya	All Participants
09:15 – 09:25	Welcome Address	Dr. R. M. Agung Harimurti, M.Kom. (Head of STMM)	Master of Ceremonies
09:25 – 09:35	Opening Remarks	Bonifasius Wahyu Pudjianto, Ph.D. (Head of Agency for HR Development on Communications & Digital Affairs)	Master of Ceremonies
09:35 – 09:45	Declaration of International Collaboration	Foreign Partnership Announcement	Master of Ceremonies
09:45 – 09:55	Keynote Speaker I	Nezar Patria, S.Fil., M.Sc., M.B.A. (Vice Minister of Communications & Digital Affairs)	Master of Ceremonies
09:55 – 10:15	Keynote Speaker II	Mussa Niyazov, Ph.D (Esil University, Kazakhstan)	Master of Ceremonies
10:15 – 10:25	Certificate Presentation to Speakers		
10:25 – 10:30	Photo Session	Group photo of speakers, guests, and participants	Documentation Team

10:30 – 10:35	Study Center Grand Opening Announcement	Study Center Opening continues at GTD (split team); the Conference will proceed.	Master of Ceremonies
10:40 – 10:55	Plenary Session I	Richard Lomotey, Ph.D. (Pennsylvania State University, USA)	Moderator
10:55 – 11:10	Plenary Session II	Prof. Mustafa Mat Deris, Ph.D. (Universiti Muhammadiyah Malaysia)	Moderator
11:10 – 11:25	Plenary Session III	Prof. Dr. Normakhmad Ravshanov (Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies & AI, Uzbekistan)	Moderator
11:25 – 11:40	Plenary Session IV	Dr. Sudono, M.Si. (STMM Yogyakarta)	Moderator
11:40 – 11:55	Discussion Session	Panel discussion with plenary speakers	Moderator & Plenary Speaker
11:55 – 12:00	Announcement of Parallel Sessions	Instructions and room assignments for breakout sessions	Organizing Committee
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch Break	Lunch	All Participants
13:00 – 15:30	Parallel Sessions / Paper Presentations	Breakout rooms (Hybrid: ~10 papers per room, each paper 10 minutes)	Moderator & Technical Support
15:30 – 16:00	Panel Discussion & Q&A	Recognition (e.g. Best Presenter per room), closing remarks	Moderator
16:00 – 16:15	Awarding & Closing Ceremony		Award Committee
16:15 – 16:30	Group Photo & Networking	Final group photo and networking	Documentation / Liaison Team

PRESENTATION SCHEDULE

SEKOLAH TINGGI MULTI MEDIA

JL. MAGELANG KM 6 YOGYAKARTA, INDONESIA

Presentation Schedule

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Room	No	Time	Presenters	Affiliation	Research Topics
Offline					
Room: R. 1.01.02 Moderator: David Kristiadi Topic: Digital Technology & Innovation	1	13.15 - 13.30	David Kristiadi; Arum Marwati	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Video Streaming Client Using HTML 5
	2	13.30 - 13.45	Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Juniana Husna; Kartikadyota Kusumaningtyas; Muhammad Ilyas Ardiansyah	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Implementing AI-Driven Big Data Analytics for Evidence-Based Public Communication Strategies: Insights from the Indonesian Context
	3	13.45 - 14.00	Rizqi Pranata	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Web3 Gaming Prospects: A Case Study of the Sandbox
	4	14.00 - 14.15	Zahra Arwananing Tyas; Mustafa Mat Deris; Iwan Riyadi Yanto	Zahra Arwananing Tyas (Universiti Muhammadiyah Malaysia); Mustafa Mat Deris (Universiti Muhammadiyah Malaysia, Malaysia); Iwan Riyadi Yanto (Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Indonesia)	Soft Set Theory in Association Rules: From Concept to Integration and Applications
	5	14.15 - 14.30	R.M Joko Priyono; Sigit Winarso; RB Hendri Kuswantoro; Willhelmus Filianto	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	An Analytical Study on the Implementation of Game-Based Learning Through Interactive Narrative in a Pixel-Art Life Simulation Game:

					A Case Study of "Citampi Stories"
	6	14.30 - 14.45	Dhety Chusumastuti; Diana Khuntari; Dina Dwika Oktora; Sony Wibisono; Anindya Damayanti; Abang Zikri Al Hafiz	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Analysis of the Digitization of Regional Innovation Administration: The Implementation of the One Data Portal of Research and Innovation (BI-SMART) at Baperrida Boyolali
	7	15.00 - 15.15	Inasari Widiyastuti; Agus Rahayu; Ratih Hurriyati; Lili Wibowo	Inasari Widiyastuti (Ministry of Communication and Digital, Indonesia & Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia); Agus Rahayu (Indonesia University of Education, Indonesia); Ratih Hurriyati (UPI, Indonesia); Lili Wibowo (Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia)	The Impact of Digital Creativity and Pricing on Game Success: Evidence from STEAM Power Database
	8	15.15 - 15.30	Marwan Marwan; Eko KH Wahyunto; Ikhwan Kurniawan Hadi Putra; Agil Puji Mukti Widodo	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Ethical Paradoxes, Legal Regulations, and Digital Communication Practices: An Analysis of Hate Speech from the Perspective of the ITE Law in Indonesia
Room: R. 1.01.04 Moderator: Ardian Setio Utomo Topic: Media and Broadcasting	1	13.15 - 13.30	Sudono Sudono; Basirun Basirun; Kusumo Gambriyanto; Oky Dewantara; Nayla Suciанти Koswara	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Reframing Multicultural Values in Public Broadcasting: A Comparative Study of TVRI (Indonesia), CBC (Canada), BBC (UK), and ABC (Australia) in the Digital Era

	2	13.30 - 13.45	Marwiyati Marwiyati; Margareth Dyah Anggraini Widirahayu; Lilik Jatmiko Prasetyo; Arga Fiananta; Irwan Chris Yulianto	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	LPP TVRI East Java's Strategy for Conveying Development Messages to Gen Z Through Multiplatform Content
	3	13.45 - 14.00	Irawan Irawan; Marwan Marwan; Sigit Purnomo; Oky Dewantara; Katarina Likahayu	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	The Role of 'E- Word of Mouth' in Image Enhancement "Nepal Van Java" Tourist Village Magelang, Central Java
	4	14.00 - 14.15	Shinta Dewi Kusumaningrum; Mufadhol Mufadhol; Kelik Erlambang; Basirun Basirun; Kusumo Gambriyanto; Kamila Nauli Panggabean	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Measuring the Audience Ratings of TVRI Sport Broadcasts Using the Arianna Nielsen Approach
	5	14.15 - 14.30	Shinto Dwirawati; Siti Sarifah; Ardian Setio Utomo; Ahmad Abuzar Al Hamdani	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Broadcast Program Innovations at RRI Surakarta and RRI Semarang
	6	14.30 - 14.45	Sintar Nababan	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Public Relations Policy Analysis to Improve the Organization's Image
	7	15.00 - 15.15	Yuni Wulandari; Jordan Oloan; Nadialila Josepika Saintera; Ade Wahyudin	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	The Effectiveness of RRI's Transformation Strategy in Engaging Generation Z in Yogyakarta
	8	15.15 - 15.30	Diyah Ayu Karunianingsih; Yolanda	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Artificial Intelligence Literacy for

			Presiana Desi; Ardian Setio Utomo; Fatikha Akfini Anantaputri		Elementary School Teachers: A Case Study in Magelang Regency
Room: R. 1.01.05 Moderator: Oky Dewantara Topic: Creative Content, Animation, AI	1	13.15 - 13.30	Anton Budi Setyawan, M.Sn; Aflah Hanif Hariadi	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	"Timun Mungsu Duren": Concept Art as Visual Critical Theory in Revitalizing Javanese Saloka"
	2	13.30 - 13.45	Siti Sarifah; Edit Rusnita	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Innovation Model in News Content Production at IDN Times Jakarta
	3	13.45 - 14.00	Dina Dwika Oktora; Sony Wibisono; Dhety Chusumastuti; Krisnawan Hartanto; Abang Zikri Al Hafiz	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	The Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the Production of Government Educational Content: A Case Study at Dinas Komunikasi Informatika Dan Persandian of Yogyakarta City
	4	14.00 - 14.15	Atmaja Septa Miyosa; Sarwanto Sarwanto; Selvi Faristasari; Helen Maria Samosir	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Narrative Structure in Animation: Educational Storytelling Approach at MD Animation Studio
	5	14.15 - 14.30	Kundori Kundori; Edi Giantoro; Joehananto Joehananto; Heriyanto Heriyanto; Ari Mintarti; Nadialila Josepika Saintera	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Analysis of the Effectiveness of Promotional Video Content in Increasing Product Sales for the Donan Cilacap Farmers Group on Social Media

	6	14.30 - 14.45	Aura Rahma Syafira; Muhammad Alief Pasha; Bintarto Wicaksono	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	A Content Analysis of "Sound Horeg Menghibur Warga!?" in the Tretan Universe Podcast
	7	15.00 - 15.15	Dwi K Relawati	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Redaction Management of the Dialogue Program of Sorot Prestasi at RRI Surakarta in the Context of the Media and Digital Transformation
	8	15.15 - 15.30	Akhmad Syaiful Anwar; Samuel Gandang Gunanto; Ginanjar Setyo Nugroho; Nurhadi Nurhadi	Akhmad Syaiful Anwar, Samuel Gandang Gunanto, Ginanjar Setyo Nugroho and Nurhadi Nurhadi (Institut Seni Indonesia Yogyakarta, Indonesia)	Genre Fusion Strategy and the Aesthetics of Dark Fantasy in the Visual Adaptation of the Alengka Kingdom in Contemporary Animation
Room: R. 1.01.06 Moderator: Arum Marwati Topic: Digital Literacy	1	13.15 - 13.30	Rizqi None Mutqiyah, M.Sc; Muhammad Danu Winata; Muhammad Fakhri Wijayanto; Wahyu Mahesa Miarta; Muhammad Abduh	Rizqi None Mutqiyah, M.Sc (Universitas Negeri Surabaya Kampus 5 Magetan, Indonesia); Muhammad Danu Winata (Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia); Muhammad Fakhri Wijayanto (Nalanda University, India); Wahyu Mahesa Miarta and Muhammad Abduh (Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia)	Parental Digital Literacy and the Normalization of Symbolic Violence in Indonesian Children's Animation: A Case Study of Tung Tung Sahur
	2	13.30 - 13.45	Siti Asiatun; Dwi Setiawan; Ernawati Ernawati; Wiwin Iripina	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Enhancing Students' Information Literacy Through Multimedia-Based Digital Communication

				Strategies in Islamic Education
3	13.45 - 14.00	Dwi Setiawan; Siti Asiatun; Dwi K Relawati; Muhammad Immawan Aulia; Rizky Andhika Surya	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Mapping Digital Interaction Networks Among Islamic High School Students Using Social Network Analysis
4	14.00 - 14.15	Fahrizal Lukman Budiono; Yuni Afita Sari; Willani Oktaviyani	Fahrizal Lukman Budiono, Yuni Afita Sari and Willani Oktaviyani (Ministry of Communications and Digital Affairs, Indonesia)	Bridging the Digital Divide Through Literacy: A Spatial and Socio-Demographic Analysis of Digital Literacy Based on Indonesia's Digital Society Index (IMDI) 2025
5	14.15 - 14.30	Nopriadi Nopriadi; Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Diana Khuntari; Arum Marwati	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Understanding and Readiness of Schools in Managing Student Personal Data Security: An Empirical Study at Vocational High Schools in Manado
6	14.30 - 14.45	Lidwina Mutia Sadasri; Rajiyem Rajiyem; Y.A. Nunung Prajarto	Lidwina Mutia Sadasri (Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia); Rajiyem Rajiyem (Gadjah Mada University, Indonesia); Y.A. Nunung Prajarto (Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia)	Health Communication in the Media (Study of Published Literature in 2020-2025)
7	15.00 - 15.15	Siti Chotijah; Bambang Sudjarwadi; Abiano Al Affan; Ramanda Fawwas Lazuardi	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Dissemination of Public Information Through Tourism Policy on Digital Media (Case Study Dissemination of Information Tourism Policy by the Ministry of Tourism)

	8	15.15 - 15.30	Arum Marwati; Diana Khuntari; Candra Santosa; I Wayan Jepriana; Adella Sesiana Putri	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia	Web-Based Application Maintenance in Small Teams at School of Multi Media
	9	15.30 - 15.45	Kautsarina Kautsarina; Yolanda Presiana Desi; Fahrizal Lukman Budiono	Kautsarina Kautsarina (Ministry of ICT, Indonesia); Yolanda Presiana Desi (Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia); Fahrizal Lukman Budiono (Ministry of Communication and Digital Affairs, Indonesia & School of Multimedia, Indonesia)	From Framework to Practice: Integrating the 4Cs Online Risk Model and Operational Digital Security Components in First-Year Digital Literacy Education

Online

Zoom Breakout Room 1 R. 1.01.01 Moderator: Krisnawan Topic: IT & AI	1	13.15 - 13.30	Yunianita Rahmawati; Mochammad Luthfan Hakim	Yunianita Rahmawati and Mochammad Luthfan Hakim (Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia)	Inventory Information System and Monitoring of Laboratory Equipment Using QR Code Website- Based
	2	13.30 - 13.45	Mochamad Alfan Rosid; Muhammad Zidny Ilhami	Mochamad Alfan Rosid and Muhammad Zidny Ilhami (Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia)	Web-Based Neighborhood Association Financial Information System
	3	13.45 - 14.00	Deva Martha Shella; Ade Eviyanti	Deva Martha Shella (Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia); Ade Eviyanti (Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember Surabaya, Indonesia)	Implementation of the K-Means Algorithm for Clustering the KBIH Jabal Nur Hajj Pilgrim Area
	4	14.00 - 14.15	Hafidha Arfiah; Abd Rahim Rahman; Safa Safiera; Tody Ariefianto	Hafidha Arfiah, Abd Rahim Rahman, Safa Safiera, Tody Ariefianto Wibowo and Sri Astuti (Telkom University, Indonesia)	The Impact of SBERT Encoder and Indexer Selection on Semantic Search

		Wibowo; Sri Astuti		Quality and Efficiency
5	14.15 - 14.30	Mochamad Alfian Rosid; Galuh Reqa Adji	Mochamad Alfian Rosid and Galuh Reqa Adji (Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia)	Design and Development of a Security and Door Control System with Monitoring for a Server Room Based on Android
6	14.30 - 14.45	Mochammad Tanzil Multazam; Bobur Sobirov	Mochammad Tanzil Multazam (Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, Indonesia); Bobur Sobirov (Samarkand, Uzbekistan)	Legal Framework for Digital Evidence Authentication in Cybercrime: Towards Secure IoT and AI Ecosystems
7	15.00 - 15.15	Christiany Juditha	Christiany Juditha (Ministry of Communication and Digital, Indonesia & Center for Human Resource Development and Research of the Communication and Informaticse Medan, Indonesia)	Online Gambling in Indonesia: Gambling Industry Trends on Digital Platforms and Government Preventive Efforts
8	15.15 - 15.30	Ernando Rizki Dalimunthe; Adam Yakriya Puri; Ananda Satrio Wicaksono; Jaka Persada Sembiring; Muhammad Anwar Sadat Faidar	Ernando Rizki Dalimunthe (Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung, Indonesia); Adam Yakriya Puri, Ananda Satrio Wicaksono, Jaka Persada Sembiring and Muhammad Anwar Sadat Faidar (Universitas Teknokrat Indonesia, Indonesia)	SPICE: Smart Precision IoT-Controlled Environment for Chili Seedling Irrigation
9	15.45 - 16.00	Rio Fiorido Panggabean; Niken Cahyani; Fazmah Arif Yulianto	Rio Fiorido Panggabean (TelkomUniversity, Indonesia & Telkom University, Indonesia); Niken Cahyani and Fazmah Arif Yulianto (Telkom University, Indonesia)	Comparative Analysis of Static and Dynamic Physical Acquisition Methods for Drone Based Data Collection

	10	16.00 - 16.15	Risna Purwita Siwi; Yudi Prayudi; Niken Cahyani	Risna Purwita Siwi (Telkom University, Indonesia); Yudi Prayudi (Universitas Islam Indonesia, Indonesia); Niken Cahyani (Telkom University, Indonesia)	Threat Modeling Analysis Using STRIDE for Secure Forensic Report Sharing
	11	16.15 - 16.30	Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Yoyok Darmanto	Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media, Indonesia; Yoyok Darmanto (Badan Siber Dan Sandi Negara, Indonesia)	Technical Analysis, Impact, and National Cybersecurity Lessons from the Brain Cipher Ransomware Attack on PDNS 2 Surabaya
Zoom Breakout Room 2 R. 1.01.03 Moderator: Anindya Damayanti Topic: Media and Communication	1	13.15 - 13.30	Anugrayani Bustamin; Inasari Widiyastuti; Marsha Carolince; Nabila Salsabila Akbar Sappe	Anugrayani Bustamin (Hasanuddin University, Indonesia); Inasari Widiyastuti (Ministry of Communication and Digital, Indonesia & Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia); Marsha Carolince and Nabila Salsabila Akbar Sappe (Universitas Hasanuddin, Indonesia)	Inclusive AI Governance Through Co-Design: Practice Lessons from Digital Services for Disabilities and Policy Recommendations
	2	13.30 - 13.45	Khrisna Wijaya Rudianto; Akmal Nafis Zaidan; Ika Yulianti; Troy Troy	Khrisna Wijaya Rudianto, Akmal Nafis Zaidan and Ika Yulianti (Institut Seni Indonesia Yogyakarta, Indonesia); Troy Troy (Institut Seni Indonesia Yogyakarta, Ascension Island)	The Utilization of Somber Colors in the Depiction of Characters, Employing Painting Techniques, Serves to Elicit a Melancholic Sentiment in the 3D Animated Film Entitled "2%"
	3	13.45 - 14.00	Rieka Mustika; Ade Sobandi; Cut Zellatifanny	Rieka Mustika and Ade Sobandi (Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia); Cut Zellatifanny (Ministry of Communication and	Strategic Adaptability in the Digital Era: Mapping Research on Digital Leadership and Dynamic

			Information Technology, Indonesia)	Capabilities (2019-2025)	
	4	14.00 - 14.15	Gulnora Abdullaeva	Gulnora Abdullaeva (Navai State University, Uzbekistan)	Increasing Motivation or Distracting Focus? Exploring the Impact of Digital Gamification Tools on Learner Engagement and Motivation of Undergraduate Students in Uzbekistan EFL Classrooms
	5	14.15 - 14.30	Dimas Aditya Nugraha; Alfira Sofia; Atef Fahrudin	Dimas Aditya Nugraha (Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia & Kementerian Komunikasi Dan Digital, Indonesia); Alfira Sofia (Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia); Atef Fahrudin (Universitas Padjadjaran, Indonesia)	Strategic Positioning and Competitive Advantage: A Comparative Analysis of Foreign Media in Indonesia's Digital Landscape
	6	14.30 - 14.45	Tristania Pangaribuan; Oktolina Simatupang	Tristania Pangaribuan and Oktolina Simatupang (National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia)	Digital Service Innovation Towards Inclusive Public Transport for Persons with Disabilities in Indonesia
	7	15.00 - 15.15	Muhammad Nurtanto; Hamid Ramadhan Nur; Rouf Muhammad; Choyrul Anwar; Farid Mutohhari; Mustofa Abi Hamid	Muhammad Nurtanto (Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia); Hamid Ramadhan Nur and Rouf Muhammad (Politeknik Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia); Choyrul Anwar (Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia); Farid Mutohhari (Universitas Sarjanawiyata Tamansiswa, Indonesia); Mustofa Abi Hamid (Universitas	Diagnostic Trouble Box (DTB) Integrated Learning Media for Automotive Electrical Systems: Enhancing Diagnostic and Critical Thinking Competence

				Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa, Indonesia & Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Indonesia)	
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CONFERENCE PAPERS

SEKOLAH TINGGI MULTI MEDIA

JL. MAGELANG KM 6 YOGYAKARTA, INDONESIA

Conference Papers

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No	Title	Abstract	Keywords	Authors
1	Legal Framework for Digital Evidence Authentication in Cybercrime: Towards Secure IoT and AI Ecosystems	The increasing prevalence of cybercrime in the era of Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) raises urgent concerns regarding the reliability of digital evidence. This paper explores the legal challenges in authenticating digital evidence within Indonesia's judicial system, focusing on cloud-based data, IoT-generated logs, and AI-driven security analytics. Using a normative legal method and comparative analysis of ISO/IEC 27037 and NIST guidelines, the study reveals gaps in Indonesia's current regulations, particularly concerning the chain of custody and admissibility of AI-assisted forensics. The paper proposes a robust legal framework that integrates certified digital forensic professionals, standardized audit trails, and judicial oversight to ensure the credibility of digital evidence in cybercrime litigation.	Blockchain; Cryptocurrency; Bitcoin; DEFI	Mochammad Tanzil Multazam; Bobur Sobirov

2	<p>Online Gambling in Indonesia: Gambling Industry Trends on Digital Platforms and Government Preventive Efforts</p>	<p>Online gambling in Indonesia has led to serious consequences, including violence, suicide, and financial misuse, showing its deep impact on public mental health. Despite being illegal, online gambling continues to grow rapidly due to technological advancements and easy digital access. Innovations such as virtual reality, artificial intelligence, and integrated payment systems further accelerate its expansion while creating new social, legal, and cultural challenges. Government efforts to address this issue include website blocking, law enforcement, international cooperation, and public awareness campaigns. This study highlights the need for a comprehensive prevention strategy involving stronger regulation, public education, and collaboration among government bodies, educational institutions, NGOs, and the tech industry. Rehabilitation and psychological support programs are also essential for affected individuals. Overall, the risks and social harms of online gambling far outweigh its economic benefits, reinforcing the need for strict oversight and continuous public education to maintain Indonesia's social and moral stability.</p>	<p>online gambling; gambling industry trends; digital platform; technologi intergrations; advertising</p>	<p>Christiany Juditha</p>
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3	<p>Parental Digital Literacy and the Normalization of Symbolic Violence in Indonesian Children's Animation: A Case Study of Tung Tung Sahur</p>	<p>Children's animation is widely consumed, yet some popular shows contain hidden forms of violence presented as humor. <i>Tung Tung Sahur</i>, a viral Indonesian animation, has raised concerns for its repeated use of verbal aggression, bullying, and slapstick targeted at young audiences. This study asks how parental digital literacy shapes the way symbolic violence in the animation is perceived and normalized. Using a qualitative approach, interviews with ten parents and visual content analysis were conducted. Drawing on Bourdieu's concept of symbolic violence, Livingstone's digital literacy framework, and Normalization Process Theory, the study examines how humor can act as subtle domination, how parents interpret aggressive content, and how repeated exposure can normalize it in family viewing. Results show that digitally literate parents are more likely to recognize and critically mediate violent elements, while those with lower literacy often see the content as harmless. Limited critical mediation combined with repeated exposure leads to gradual normalization of aggressive humor in children's daily lives. The study highlights the need for improved parental guidance and stronger critical digital literacy to support responsible media consumption in Indonesia.</p>	<p>Parental Digital Literacy; Symbolic Violence; Children's Animation; Normalization Process; Audience Interpretation</p>	<p>Rizqi Mutqiyah, M.Sc; Muhammad Danu Winata; Muhammad Fakhri Wijayanto; Wahyu Mahesa Miarta; Muhammad Abduh</p>
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4	SPICE: Smart Precision IoT-Controlled Environment for Chili Seedling Irrigation	<p>Manual watering of chili plants often leads to inconsistent soil moisture, which can disrupt early plant development. This study applies an IoT-based system to automate the monitoring and irrigation of chili seedlings. The system uses an ESP32 microcontroller, two soil moisture sensors, a relay module, and a 12V DC pump, with real-time sensor data displayed through the Blynk application for remote supervision and control via mobile devices. The research involves hardware and software design, sensor calibration, and three days of field testing in Sungai Langka Village, Pesawaran. The results show that the system maintains soil moisture within the optimal 60–80% range, automatically turning the pump on when moisture drops below the set threshold and off once desired levels are restored. This ensures more consistent watering and prevents over- or under-irrigation. By integrating IoT technology, the system increases water-use efficiency, minimizes manual intervention, and supports healthier and more uniform chili seedling growth. Overall, the study demonstrates that IoT-based automation offers an effective approach to agricultural modernization and contributes to the development of sustainable smart farming practices.</p>	Internet of Things (IoT); Soil Moisture Sensor; Chili Seedling; Agricultural Automation; Blynk	Ernando Rizki Dalimunthe; Adam Yakriya Puri; Ananda Satrio Wicaksono; Jaka Persada Sembiring; Muhammad Anwar Sadat Faidar
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5	<p>The Impact of Digital Creativity and Pricing on Game Success: Evidence from STEAM Power Database</p>	<p>The digital game industry plays a major role in the global creative economy, yet the way creativity contributes to market success is not fully understood. This study explores how digital creativity and pricing strategies influence game performance using behavioural data from 9,455 Steam titles. A new Digital Creativity Index (DCI) was created by combining creativity residuals, engagement efficiency, and release-normalized traction to measure creativity as an outcome-based capability rather than a subjective perception. The analysis using OLS regression shows that digital creativity significantly improves player ratings and engagement, confirming its role as a dynamic capability that supports long-term competitive advantage. Creativity also strengthens the effect of pricing, indicating that more creative games increase players' willingness to pay by signalling higher quality. Cluster analysis identifies three strategic patterns: Creative Hits, Price-Oriented Performers, and Community Builders, with creativity-driven games achieving the strongest and most durable success. Overall, the study expands innovation-based competitive advantage theory by introducing a behavioural metric for creativity and demonstrating how creativity and pricing jointly influence value creation in the digital game market.</p>	<p>digital creativity; game success; innovation; competitive advantage; game creativity</p>	<p>Inasari Widiyastuti; Agus Rahayu; Ratih Hurriyati; Lili Wibowo</p>
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6	Dissemination of Public Information Through Tourism Policy on Digital Media (Case Study Dissemination of Information Tourism Policy by the Ministry of Tourism)	Digital media has become the main source of information for Indonesians, with 143 million social media users recorded in 2025 and internet penetration surpassing 68%. Platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram dominate daily use, making digital media an essential channel for distributing public information and shaping public perception. This study examines how the Ministry of Tourism utilizes digital platforms to communicate, promote, and implement tourism policies. Using a qualitative descriptive approach based on documentation, observation, and interviews, the research finds that digital media strengthens transparency, accessibility, and public engagement. The Ministry employs official websites, social media, and online campaigns to expand outreach and build a positive tourism image. Despite these benefits, challenges persist, including message consistency, uneven digital literacy, and the complexity of managing public feedback. The study concludes that effective digital dissemination requires coordinated communication strategies and collaboration across sectors to improve public understanding and participation in tourism development.	Digital media; Tourism; The Ministry of Tourism; Policy; Public information; Dissemination	Siti Chotijah; Bambang Sudjarwadi; Abiano Al Affan; Ramanda Fawwas Lazuardi
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7	"Timun Mungsu Duren": Concept Art as Visual Critical Theory in Revitalizing Javanese Saloka"	<p>This practice-based research examines how concept art can function as “visual critical theory” to revitalize intangible cultural heritage. Using the Javanese saloka <i>Timun Mungsu Duren</i> as a case study, it employs a mimetic-deconstructive approach to move beyond textual interpretation and uncover the proverb’s semiotic layers and power relations. Through Derrida’s <i>différance</i>, the study deconstructs binary oppositions like strong/weak and winner/loser, opening space for subversive reinterpretation. The artistic process transforms textual wisdom into visual narratives, producing concept art that serves as both contemporary artwork and intellectual asset. The study contributes by showing the value of combining Foucault’s power–resistance ideas with Derridean deconstruction, demonstrating how visual hermeneutics fosters intergenerational dialogue through flexible meaning, and positioning concept art as a legitimate academic method for cultural critique. Overall, the research shows how cultural metaphors can become intellectual property that enriches the creative and cultural ecosystem, while highlighting digital art practice as an effective tool for cultural preservation, critique, and transformation.</p>	Concept Art; Visual Critical Theory; Cultural Revitalization; Deconstruction; Javanese Saloka; Practice-Based Research	Anton Budi Setyawan, M.Sn; Aflah Hanif Hariadi
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8	<p>Reframing Multicultural Values in Public Broadcasting: A Comparative Study of TVRI (Indonesia), CBC (Canada), BBC (UK), and ABC (Australia) in the Digital Era</p>	<p>Public service broadcasters (PSBs) are tasked with promoting social cohesion and cultural diversity, yet digital transformation has reshaped how they frame and communicate multicultural values. This study compares TVRI East Java with CBC (Canada), BBC (UK), and ABC (Australia) to understand how different political and technological contexts influence their approaches. Using constructivist theory and framing analysis, the research draws on content analysis, policy review, and interviews with editorial leaders. TVRI emphasizes national harmony grounded in Pancasila, CBC highlights minority representation and inclusion, BBC focuses on institutional diversity, and ABC frequently adopts social justice and accountability frames. Despite these differences, all broadcasters face similar pressures, including digital disruption, audience fragmentation, and the need to upgrade newsroom capacities. The study provides a cross-cultural perspective on how PSBs construct multicultural news and shows how socio-political environments shape their narratives. It concludes that strengthening public broadcasting requires integrated digital strategies and renewed commitments to inclusive and democratic communication in the digital era.</p>	<p>multiculturalism ; public service broadcasting; framing; digital transformation; comparative journalism</p>	<p>Sudono Sudono; Basirun Basirun; Kusumo Gambriyanto ; Oky Dewantara; Nayla Sucianti Koswara</p>
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9	Innovation Model in News Content Production at IDN Times Jakarta	<p>The rapid digital era has shifted news consumption from traditional media to digital platforms, creating greater demands for speed, personalization, and interactivity. In this landscape, innovation in digital entertainment platforms is crucial for media organizations to optimize production and meet market needs. IDN Times has become a leading digital media player for Millennials and Gen-Z through the IDN App, which won the Gold Winner for Best Innovative Digital Product at WAN-IFRA 2025. This achievement reflects IDN's strong digital innovation and its ability to maintain growth amid industry challenges, including the shutdown of broadcasting companies and rising layoffs. This study examines IDN Times Jakarta's innovation model in news production that contributed to winning the award. Using a descriptive qualitative method with purposive sampling, the research collects data from selected informants, supported by literature review and platform observations. The study aims to uncover how IDN Times develops and applies digital innovation in its workflows. The expected outcome is to identify IDN Times' news production innovation model and provide insights that can serve as an evaluation framework to improve digital-era news production and strengthen digital journalism practices.</p>	Digital Media; IDN Apps; News Production Innovation; IDN Times	Siti Sarifah; Edit Rusnita
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10	LPP TVRI East Java's Strategy for Conveying Development Messages to Gen Z Through Multiplatform Content	<p>Digital transformation requires LPP TVRI East Java to adapt in order to stay relevant in delivering development messages to Generation Z. This study analyzes TVRI East Java's strategy for producing and distributing development content across multiple digital platforms. A descriptive qualitative method was used, with data gathered through interviews with the Program Manager and Creative Team. The findings show that TVRI East Java's strategy is shaped by data identifying Gen Z as the dominant social media audience. The main approach is "multi-format packaging," adapting terrestrial programs into short digital formats 1–5 minutes for TikTok and Instagram, and about 10 minutes for YouTube. TikTok is prioritized for news engagement, while Instagram is used for entertainment content. To improve message reception, the creative team applies an "honest, relatable, and authentic" communication style with refreshed framing for traditional topics. The study also finds that collaborations with influencers and Surabaya State University students significantly boost engagement, outperforming visual editing improvements alone. Overall, TVRI East Java successfully balances its educational mission with Gen Z's digital consumption patterns.</p>	Broadcasting Strategy; Multiplatform Content; LPP TVRI; Gen Z; Development Message	Marwiyati Marwiyati; Margareth Dyah Anggraini Widirahayu; Lilik Jatmiko Prasetyo; Arga Fiananta; Irwan Chris Yulianto
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11	The Role of 'E-Word of Mouth' in Image Enhancement "Nepal Van Java" Tourist Village Magelang, Central Java	<p>This study examines the role of electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM) in strengthening the image of Nepal Van Java (NVJ) Tourism Village in Magelang, Central Java, and identifies the digital platforms and content types shaping this image. Using a descriptive qualitative method with purposive sampling, five informants three loyal visitors and two social media content creators were interviewed. Data were gathered through interviews, observation, and documentation, then analysed using the Miles and Huberman interactive model. The findings show that e-WOM significantly helps build a positive image of NVJ through authentic tourist-generated content on Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp. Panoramic photos, travel vlogs, and personal testimonials create the perception of NVJ as an exotic and welcoming destination, encouraging visitor satisfaction and loyalty. This positive cycle develops organically without direct managerial involvement. The study concludes that e-WOM serves as an effective organic branding strategy for community-based tourism. Practically, NVJ managers should manage e-WOM through official social media, improve service quality, and involve the community as digital ambassadors to sustain NVJ's positive image in the digital era.</p>	e-Word of Mouth; destination image; tourist village; Nepal Van Java; social media	Irawan Irawan; Marwan Marwan; Sigit Purnomo; Oky Dewantara; Katarina Likahayu
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12	Ethical Paradoxes, Legal Regulations, and Digital Communication Practices: An Analysis of Hate Speech from the Perspective of the ITE Law in Indonesia	<p>This study examines the tension between ethics, legal regulations, and digital communication in Indonesia, focusing on Articles 27 and 28 of the Electronic Information and Transactions (ITE) Law. Using a Communication Law approach combining legal dogmatics, theory, and philosophy, it assesses whether digital legal norms align with justice, morality, and freedom of expression. The findings show that the ITE Law suffers from serious normative and institutional flaws. The vague wording of Article 27(3) and Article 28(2) violates <i>lex certa</i> and <i>rechtszekerheid</i>, creating risks of opinion criminalization and limiting freedom of expression. Digital communication monitoring is also fragmented across institutions, weakening enforcement. The study proposes a Constitutional Digital Communication Legal System Model consisting of constitutional normative principles, an independent National Information Technology Commission (KTIN), clearer reformulation of ITE norms, and stronger public digital literacy. The research reinforces the Democratic Rule of Law and advances Integrative Law and Communication System theory, aiming to build a legal system that balances freedom of expression, accountability, and public ethics in Indonesia's digital democracy.</p>	ITE Law; digital communication law; hate speech; communication ethics; National Information Technology Commission	Marwan Marwan; Eko KH Wahyunto; Ikhwan Kurniawan Hadi Putra; Agil Puji Mukti Widodo
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13	<p>Inclusive AI Governance Through Co-Design: Practice Lessons from Digital Services for Disabilities and Policy Recommendations</p>	<p>Artificial intelligence is becoming central to digital transformation, yet people with disabilities still face barriers due to non-adaptive interfaces, limited accessibility features, and low digital literacy. This study proposes inclusive AI-supported solutions through a co-design approach based on the Social Model of Disability and Public Service Logic. Workshops and accessibility audits in Yogyakarta and Makassar show that voice interaction, automated captioning, and adaptive interfaces can enhance digital inclusion, although their adoption in public services is still limited. The co-design process engaged persons with disabilities, developers, and policymakers to identify barriers and create more accessible prototypes. Findings show that accessibility involves fairness, ethics, and usability, not only technical improvements. Insights highlight the need for multimodal interaction, awareness of cognitive load, and AI tools to assess accessibility. Despite national commitments, the lack of enforceable standards and limited coordination continue to hinder progress. The study recommends stronger accessibility requirements in AI governance, improved procurement practices, and expanded capacity-building to support a more inclusive digital ecosystem for persons with disabilities.</p>	<p>Inclusive AI; Co-design; Digital service transformation; disabilities; Human Computer Interaction</p>	<p>Anugrayani Bustamin; Inasari Widiyastuti; Marsha Carolince; Nabila Salsabila Akbar Sappe</p>
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14	<p>Analysis of the Digitization of Regional Innovation Administration: The Implementation of the One Data Portal of Research and Innovation (BI-SMART) at Baperrida Boyolali</p>	<p>The increasing need for public sector innovation positions Baperrida as the coordinator of various OPD initiatives, yet accountability is often disrupted by bureaucratic inefficiencies and fragmented information systems. To resolve this, the Boyolali Regency Government launched BI-SMART, a unified data portal for all research and innovation activities. This study analyzes BI-SMART's implementation through a qualitative descriptive approach using interviews with key Baperrida stakeholders. The findings show that BI-SMART has streamlined processes and improved innovation reporting. However, the main challenge lies not in technology but in human factors, particularly OPD staff's limited understanding of innovation concepts, leading to low reporting. The study recommends strategies to sustain BI-SMART and suggests its potential adoption by Baperrida in other regions developing unified innovation data portals.</p>	<p>Public administration; E-government; Information system; Digital transformation</p>	<p>Dhety Chusumastuti; Diana Khuntari; Dina Dwika Oktora; Sony Wibisono; Anindya Damayanti; Abang Zikri Al Hafiz</p>
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15	Genre Fusion Strategy and the Aesthetics of Dark Fantasy in the Visual Adaptation of the Alengka Kingdom in Contemporary Animation	<p>This study investigates how the Alengka Kingdom from the Ramayana is visually adapted into contemporary animation as the central antagonist. Using a qualitative approach that compares traditional depictions in temple reliefs and wayang with modern animated versions, the research analyzes iconographic changes and contemporary aesthetics. The findings show that creators use a Fantasy–Sci-Fi genre fusion and a strong Dark Fantasy aesthetic. Alengka’s classical fortress is reimagined as a dark, high-tech metropolis or cyberpunk complex, emphasizing Ravana’s image as a powerful and technologically advanced tyrant. Ravana’s visual form is simplified and humanized but still retains his core symbols of power and wrath. These adaptations aim to make the story more relevant to modern audiences, intensify the conflict, and portray Alengka as a metaphor for corrupt technological power. The study concludes that contemporary adaptation is a strategic reinterpretation that revitalizes classical iconography through modern visual language.</p>	Genre Fusion; Dark Fantasy Aesthetics; Alengka Kingdom; Contemporary Animation; Visual Analysis; Iconographic Transformation	Akhmad Syaiful Anwar; Samuel Gandang Gunanto; Ginanjar Setyo Nugroho; Nurhadi Nurhadi
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16	<p>The Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the Production of Government Educational Content: A Case Study at Dinas Komunikasi Informatika Dan Persandian of Yogyakarta City</p>	<p>The digital transformation of the public sector has encouraged government institutions to adopt innovative technologies, with Artificial Intelligence playing an increasingly important role in improving efficiency, creativity, and information delivery. This study analyzes the implementation, challenges, and impact of AI use in producing educational content at Diskominfo Yogyakarta City. Using a qualitative descriptive case study, data were gathered through interviews, observations, and documentation involving creative teams and technical staff. The findings show that AI is used across several production stages, including planning, production, and post-production, through tools such as ChatGPT, Adobe Creative Suite, and CapCut. AI has boosted work efficiency, enhanced content quality, and increased production frequency up to four times compared to the pre-AI period. Challenges remain in ethics, data security, and the absence of formal regulations for AI use in public institutions. However, skilled human resources and training efforts have helped Diskominfo adapt. The study recommends establishing SOPs, ethical guidelines, and national policies to ensure responsible and sustainable AI use in public communication.</p>	<p>Digital Transformation; Artificial Intelligence; Content Production; Public Communication; Yogyakarta City Government</p>	<p>Dina Dwika Oktora; Sony Wibisono; Dhety Chusumastuti; Krisnawan Hartanto; Abang Zikri Al Hafiz</p>
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17	Narrative Structure in Animation: Educational Storytelling Approach at MD Animation Studio	<p>The strength of creative products such as animation lies in their ability to build meaningful and engaging stories. MD Animation, known for the hit series <i>Adit Sopo Jarwo</i>, demonstrates a consistent storytelling pattern rooted in local culture and values. This study analyzes MD Animation's storytelling approach, focusing on narrative structure, key storytelling elements, and their influence on audience engagement and the national animation industry. Using a qualitative case study and narrative analysis method, the research examines MD Animation's works through observation, document review, and analysis of story structure, character development, conflict, and moral messages. The goal is to identify narrative patterns that shape the studio's creative identity. Although still ongoing, the study is expected to support the development of an Indonesian-style storytelling model reflecting local cultural identity and provide guidance for effective story-writing strategies in animation education, especially for students in the Animation Study Program at the School of Multi Media.</p>	animation; creative industry; MD Animation; narrative analysis; storytelling	Atmaja Septa Miyosa; Sarwanto Sarwanto; Selvi Faristasari; Helen Maria Samosir
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18	<p>Enhancing Students' Information Literacy Through Multimedia-Based Digital Communication Strategies in Islamic Education</p>	<p>Information literacy is essential for students to navigate complex digital information, counter misinformation, and strengthen critical thinking. SMAIT Nurul Islam Tenganan faces obstacles in optimizing multimedia technology due to limited digital infrastructure and uneven teacher skills. This study analyzes students' information literacy levels and formulates strategies to improve them through interactive multimedia. Using a qualitative descriptive approach, data were collected through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation, then analyzed inductively with source triangulation. The findings show that multimedia use significantly enhances students' ability to access, evaluate, and apply information critically and independently. However, its effectiveness is constrained by unequal technological support and the lack of school policies dedicated to digital information literacy. This study contributes to the development of multimedia-based communication strategies suitable for Islamic educational settings and offers a strategic model that can be adopted by similar institutions to strengthen students' information literacy.</p>	<p>information literacy; multimedia technology; digital communication; Islamic education; learning innovation</p>	<p>Siti Asiatun; Dwi Setiawan; Ernawati Ernawati; Wiwin Iripina</p>
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19	Mapping Digital Interaction Networks Among Islamic High School Students Using Social Network Analysis	<p>Digital technology has changed how adolescents communicate, including in Islamic-integrated schools where gender segregation and religious digital ethics influence online behavior. This study maps students' digital communication networks and examines how these norms affect information flow and academic support. Social Network Analysis was applied to four layers: digital interaction, information sharing, academic support, and teacher-mediated messages. The results show a sparse network with a density of 0.0423, meaning only a small number of possible connections are active. Centrality patterns reveal gender differences: male students tend to initiate interactions and spread information, while female students form cohesive clusters that maintain communication stability. Several students with high betweenness act as brokers connecting separate groups. Each layer has different structures and key actors, indicating that no single group dominates all digital interactions. Overall, the findings show that religious norms and school regulations shape the structure of digital communication networks. The study introduces the "Digital Adab Network" as a foundation for digital literacy development and safer communication policies in Islamic schools.</p>	Social Network Analysis; Digital Adab; Islamic School; Centrality; Gendered Network Structure; Multi-Layer Network	Dwi Setiawan; Siti Asiatun; Dwi K Relawati; Muhammad Immawan Aulia; Rizky Andhika Surya
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20	Measuring the Audience Ratings of TVRI Sport Broadcasts Using the Arianna Nielsen Approach	<p>The growth of digital technology has transformed media consumption patterns, presenting new challenges for TVRI as Indonesia's public broadcaster. Audience ratings are a key indicator of TVRI's performance, reflecting viewer interest and program reach. This study analyzes TVRI Sport's audience performance over one month using Nielsen rating data processed with Arianna. Linear regression was applied to identify rating trends and factors influencing viewer fluctuations. The results show clear patterns in audience behavior, including trend shifts, seasonal characteristics, and specific time periods with the highest and lowest performance. The highest rating occurred at 3:00 a.m. WIB with 1.64%, while the lowest was at 1:00 a.m. WIB with 0.13%. These findings contribute to mass media studies and provide strategic insights for TVRI to optimize program scheduling, improve content appeal, and strengthen its relevance in the digital era.</p>	measuring; rating; performance; TVRI; arianna	Shinta Dewi Kusumaningrum; Mufadhol Mufadhol; Kelik Erlambang; Basirun Basirun; Kusumo Gambriyanto ; Kamila Nauli Panggabean
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21	Broadcast Program Innovations at RRI Surakarta and RRI Semarang	<p>This study examines the innovation strategies adopted by RRI Surakarta and RRI Semarang in responding to digital-era media transformation. Using a qualitative descriptive method, data were collected through interviews with program managers, observations of broadcasting activities, and documentation from RRI's digital platforms. The findings show that both stations have strengthened digital content production, expanded their presence on social media, and developed streaming and podcast services to engage younger and more dispersed audiences. These efforts have widened audience reach and introduced more interactive formats while maintaining radio's core public service role. Although both stations pursue technological modernization, they remain committed to supporting government policies, promoting national values, and providing educational and culturally relevant content. The study concludes that RRI's innovations reflect a balanced approach that integrates modern media practices with its public service mission. Recommendations include continued investment in digital skills, audience research, and partnerships, with emphasis on audience analytics and community-driven programming to maintain long-term relevance.</p>	RRI; Innovation; Digital Era; Digital Content; Broadcasting Program	Shinto Dwirawati; Siti Sarifah; Ardian Setio Utomo; Ahmad Abuzar Al Hamdani
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22	<p>Bridging the Digital Divide Through Literacy: A Spatial and Socio-Demographic Analysis of Digital Literacy Based on Indonesia's Digital Society Index (IMDI) 2025</p>	<p>Indonesia's digital transformation relies on citizens' digital literacy. Although IMDI 2025 shows improvement, regional and social gaps remain. This study examines spatial patterns and socio-economic factors influencing literacy using descriptive, quantitative, and spatial analyses. The results show that provinces with better infrastructure, higher education, and active communities such as West Java, Yogyakarta, and Bali record higher literacy levels. Regions with limited internet access, fewer training programs, and socio-economic barriers such as Papua, Maluku, and parts of Nusa Tenggara remain low. These differences highlight the need for locally tailored strategies rather than uniform national programs. To address these gaps, the study proposes a Community Driven Digital Literacy Acceleration model that involves local governments, educational institutions, and communities in designing training and awareness initiatives. This approach supports more equitable digital inclusion and strengthens Indonesia's digital transformation.</p>	<p>Digital literacy; Digital divide; IMDI 2025; Digital inclusion; Community-based literacy</p>	<p>Fahrizal Lukman Budiono; Yuni Afita Sari; Willani Oktaviyani</p>
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23	Video Streaming Client Using HTML 5	<p>Computer networks can be used as a video distribution medium through file transfer or streaming. Video players can be desktop applications, mobile applications, or a web page accessed using a web browser, one of the technologies that uses HTML5. HTML5 includes several basic libraries to access website page content such as images, text, and video. HTML5's ability to access streaming video is still limited to several codecs. The web page can be accessed via the internet and a web browser. The implementation web page uses the Golang programming environment for server-side scripting, while the client-side uses HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. This research created an HTML5-based video player prototype by implementing the Dash.js, VideoJS, and Shaka player libraries. The video format to be played has the extension *.webm. An HTML5-based video player prototype was successfully created. The video player prototype can implement the DashIF, VideoJS, and Shaka Player libraries. The Shaka player implementation achieved the best performance, with the smallest number of requests and the fastest loading time. Furthermore, Shaka player offers complete functionality without needing a third plugin. If a more prosperous and more diverse user interface is required, the VideoJS player can be used, but with relatively good performance.</p>	Video Streaming; HTML 5; Dash.js; VideoJS; Shaka Player	David Kristiadi; Arum Marwati
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24	Web-Based Application Maintenance in Small Teams at School of Multi Media	<p>This study analyzes the software maintenance strategy of the SITAMA web application at the Multimedia College (STMM) using the Software Maintenance Quadrant Model. Using a descriptive qualitative approach, data were collected through purposive interviews with developers and users, direct observation, and document analysis. The findings show a clear imbalance among the four maintenance quadrants. Corrective maintenance dominates SITAMA's workflow, supported by quick coordination among developers, users, and infrastructure teams through a WhatsApp group. However, the study also identifies major issues such as poor documentation of changes, which leads to recurring bugs after updates, and the absence of formal criteria for managing or tracking technical debt. Maintenance relies heavily on informal communication, with no established procedures or official documentation. The study concludes that SITAMA requires a more structured, documented, and balanced maintenance strategy. It recommends implementing proper change documentation and strengthening preventive maintenance to enhance system reliability and usability.</p>	STMM; SITAMA; Small Team; Software Maintenance; Software Maintenance Quadrant Model	Arum Marwati; Diana Khuntari; Candra Santosa; I Wayan Jepriana; Adella Sesiana Putri
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25	Public Relations Policy Analysis to Improve the Organization's Image	<p>A positive organizational image strengthens public trust, while a negative one weakens communication effectiveness. This study analyzes the Public Relations communication strategy of the Ministry of Communication and Digital (Komdigi) in improving its institutional image and identifying message forms suited to different media. Using a qualitative descriptive approach with an exploratory case study, three purposively selected informants were involved. Data were collected through structured interviews, observations of publication media and digital communication activities, and documentation studies, then analyzed using the Miles and Huberman model. The results show that Komdigi builds public trust through four key strategies: identifying communication targets to shape a credible and sustainable image, selecting appropriate media to strengthen reputation, aligning message purposes with public needs and expectations, and optimizing the role of communicators as message designers who understand cultural values and maintain image consistency.</p>	Public Image; Government Public Relations; Communication Strategy; Ministry of Communication and Digital	Sintar Nababan
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26	<p>Understanding and Readiness of Schools in Managing Student Personal Data Security: An Empirical Study at Vocational High Schools in Manado</p>	<p>This study analyzes the awareness and readiness of vocational high schools in Manado in managing and protecting students' personal data. Using a survey method with questionnaires, the research assessed stakeholders' understanding of data privacy and the schools' capacity to implement effective protection policies. The findings show that although awareness of data protection exists, many staff and students still have limited understanding of privacy concepts and risks from data breaches. Several schools also lack comprehensive policies and adequate IT infrastructure. However, there is strong institutional commitment to data security, seen in the use of physical and technological safeguards and emerging security-oriented practices. The study recommends increasing training on data protection, developing clearer policies, and improving IT infrastructure. Strengthening these areas is expected to raise the overall readiness of vocational high schools in Manado and support a safer educational environment.</p>	<p>Personal Data Protection; Data Security Awareness; School Readiness; Information Security; Vocational High School; Manado</p>	<p>Nopriadi Nopriadi; Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Diana Khuntari; Arum Marwati</p>
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27	Diagnostic Trouble Box (DTB) Integrated Learning Media for Automotive Electrical Systems: Enhancing Diagnostic and Critical Thinking Competence	This study examines the effectiveness of Diagnostic Trouble Box (DTB)-integrated learning media in improving vocational students' diagnostic competence and critical thinking in automotive electrical systems. The DTB simulates real vehicle faults with adjustable difficulty, allowing students to practice systematic troubleshooting and decision-making similar to industry standards. Using a quasi-experimental design with 68 students, data were collected through validated diagnostic and critical thinking tests, observations, and analyzed with paired and independent t-tests. Results show that students using the DTB achieved significantly higher improvements ($p < 0.05$) than those taught conventionally. The DTB group demonstrated stronger abilities in identifying faults, interpreting data, and planning accurate repairs, indicating better analytical reasoning and problem-solving skills. The study concludes that DTB integration creates an authentic, technology-enhanced learning environment that strengthens higher-order thinking and bridges classroom learning with actual industrial diagnostic practices, preparing students for the demands of Industry 4.0.	Diagnostic Trouble Box (DTB); automotive electrical systems; diagnostic competence; critical thinking skills; vocational education; quasi-experimental design	Muhammad Nurtanto; Hamid Ramadhan Nur; Rouf Muhammad; Choyrul Anwar; Farid Mutohhari; Mustofa Abi Hamid
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28	<p>Implementing AI-Driven Big Data Analytics for Evidence-Based Public Communication Strategies: Insights from the Indonesian Context</p>	<p>In the digital communication era, organizations increasingly rely on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence to support evidence-based communication and enhance public engagement. This study examines how an Indonesian digital monitoring firm implements AI-based social media analytics and manages ethical and explainability challenges. Using a descriptive qualitative method, data were collected through interviews, workflow observations, and documentation analysis. The findings show that AI-driven analytics enables real-time sentiment tracking, trend prediction, and audience profiling, improving accuracy and responsiveness in communication strategies. However, issues remain in ensuring model transparency, reducing data bias, and maintaining ethical data governance, all of which influence trust and accountability in AI-assisted communication. The study concludes that while AI-based Big Data Analytics strengthens communication management, it must be supported by governance frameworks that prioritize explainability, transparency, and ethical responsibility. These findings offer conceptual and practical guidance for integrating responsible and explainable AI in communication analytics, particularly in rapidly evolving digital contexts like Indonesia.</p>	<p>Big Data Analytics; Explainable AI (XAI); Ethical Data Governance; Public Communication Strategy</p>	<p>Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Juniana Husna; Kartikadyota Kusumaningtyas; Muhammad Ilyas Ardiansyah</p>
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29	Analysis of the Effectiveness of Promotional Video Content in Increasing Product Sales for the Donan Cilacap Farmers Group on Social Media	<p>Digital technology has changed product marketing, making social media a key channel. In Indonesia, increasing internet access benefits MSMEs, with video content being the most effective for engagement and purchasing decisions. For agribusiness groups like KWT Donan in Cilacap, video marketing offers a way to overcome traditional marketing barriers. This study analyzes how promotional videos on social media improve KWT Donan's product sales. Using a qualitative case study, data were gathered through interviews, observation, and video documentation. The findings show that video content significantly boosted sales, increased brand awareness, expanded reach, and built consumer trust through authentic storytelling. Effective videos highlighted farmers and production processes, used local narratives, and lasted 45 seconds to 2 minutes. Challenges included limited production skills, low digital literacy, weak analytics, and inconsistent posting. The study concludes that video marketing is highly beneficial for local agribusiness, but maximizing its impact requires better skills, evaluation, and consistency.</p>	Promotional Videos; Effectiveness; Sales; Farmer Groups	Kundori Kundori; Edi Giantoro; Joehananto Joehananto; Heriyanto Heriyanto; Ari Mintarti; Nadialila Josepika Saintera
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30	<p>The Utilization of Somber Colors in the Depiction of Characters, Employing Painting Techniques, Serves to Elicit a Melancholic Sentiment in the 3D Animated Film Entitled "2%"</p>	<p>The use of somber colors and painting techniques in animated characters is often subjective, requiring empirical data to support more measurable design decisions. This study aims to identify the most preferred combinations of somber colors and painting techniques among animation practitioners and enthusiasts using a quantitative approach. An online visual survey was distributed through purposive and snowball sampling. Respondents assessed character variations featuring somber color combinations with oil texture layering, matte brushes, watercolor layering, and texture noise techniques. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to measure preference levels. The findings show that most respondents favored character designs using somber blue-gray colors combined with the oil texture layering technique. Both practitioners and enthusiasts showed similar preferences, with no significant differences between the groups. This preferred combination is recommended as a reference for enhancing visual appeal and emotional impact in animation, digital games, and other creative content.</p>	<p>somber colors; painting techniques; visual preferences; animated character design</p>	<p>Khrisna Wijaya Rudianto; Akmal Nafis Zaidan; Ika Yulianti; Troy Troy</p>
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31	Comparative Analysis of Static and Dynamic Physical Acquisition Methods for Drone Based Data Collection	<p>The rapid development of UAV or drone technology has influenced many sectors while creating new challenges in digital forensics. Because UAVs contain multiple components, communication modules, and digital storage, data acquisition becomes essential to maintain evidence integrity. This study compares two physical data acquisition methods in UAV forensics to identify the most effective and forensically reliable approach. Using an experimental method with the DJI Mini 3, data were acquired using FTK Imager 4.7.1.2 and analyzed with Autopsy 4.22.0. Evaluation focused on data integrity, artifact completeness, and metadata quality. The results show that both acquisition methods produced identical MD5 and SHA-1 hash values, confirming evidence integrity. Both methods also yielded similar artifact and metadata quantities, indicating comparable effectiveness. The static method was found more suitable for post-incident validation because it offers better control and reduces contamination risks. The dynamic method is more appropriate for field situations that require fast data capture while the UAV is still active. Overall, both methods complement each other and can be integrated into a UAV forensic acquisition framework to support digital investigations.</p>	Drone Forensics; Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV); Static Physical Acquisition; Dynamic Physical Acquisition; Digital Forensics	Rio Fiorido Panggabean; Niken Cahyani; Fazmah Arif Yulianto
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32	The Effectiveness of RRI's Transformation Strategy in Engaging Generation Z in Yogyakarta	<p>This study evaluates the effectiveness of RRI's digital transformation strategy in attracting Generation Z audiences in Yogyakarta. Using a quantitative descriptive survey of 124 respondents, the research examines audience perceptions, media habits, and expectations toward RRI's digital services. Results show that although RRI has implemented digital features such as live streaming, podcasts, and social media distribution, audience awareness remains moderate (mean 3.34). In contrast, preferences for digital channels and podcasts are high (mean 3.84 and 3.98). Major obstacles include the dominance of alternative media and limited promotion of RRI's digital platforms. Generation Z expresses strong interest in interactive and engaging content and expects RRI to be more active on platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. The study concludes that RRI's digital transformation is progressing but has not yet effectively captured Generation Z's attention. To improve its appeal, RRI needs stronger visibility, better content quality, and higher interactivity through social-first strategies, flexible on-demand formats, two-way engagement, and collaboration with creative communities and educational institutions.</p>	Radio Republik Indonesia; Digital Transformation; Generation Z; Social Media; Podcast	Yuni Wulandari; Jordan Oloan; Nadialila Josepika Saintera; Ade Wahyudin; Isnaeni Nurrohmah; Elan Baskara
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33	A Content Analysis of "Sound Horeg Menghibur Warga!?" in the Tretan Universe Podcast	<p>In the digital communication era, podcasts have become a popular medium for Indonesians to share information informally. One episode of the Tretan Universe podcast, "Sound Horeg Menghibur Warga!?", discusses the trending sound horeg phenomenon. This study analyses how the podcast structures and presents its content on this topic using a descriptive content analysis approach. Data were collected through manual transcription of dialogue and visuals, supported by online articles and related literature.</p> <p>Transcripts were categorized into themes such as factual information, humour, cultural context, news elements, and narrative flow. The findings show that the episode blends entertainment and information through humour, casual conversation, and fact-based narration. Although dominated by entertainment, it still reflects journalistic qualities by providing background context, citing information sources, and offering accurate explanations. The episode functions as a hybrid format that merges entertainment with alternative journalism, demonstrating how Indonesian content creators use podcasts to discuss social and cultural issues in an engaging and accessible way.</p>	podcast; content analysis; youtube; sound horeg	Aura Rahma Syafira; Muhammad Alief Pasha; Bintarto Wicaksono
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34	Web3 Gaming Prospects: A Case Study of the Sandbox	<p>The Web3 revolution introduces decentralization and true digital asset ownership through blockchain, and The Sandbox stands out as a platform that transforms this technology into an intuitive gaming experience. This study explores how The Sandbox utilizes Web3 to shape its distinctive user experience using a descriptive qualitative approach. Following Suci Hartati's view on transferability, the research ensures its findings remain relevant across contexts.</p> <p>Analysis of The Sandbox's three main components VoxEdit for asset creation, the Marketplace for NFT trading, and Game Maker for building experiences shows that immersive visual design and simple drag-and-drop mechanics create strong user engagement. The platform demonstrates that Web3 can be integrated smoothly into gameplay without reducing comfort or enjoyment. The study concludes that The Sandbox succeeds by making Web3 feel natural within the gaming experience. Its accessible interface design becomes a key factor in supporting wider adoption of Web3-based games.</p>	The Sandbox; Web3; User Experience; Technology; User Interface	Rizqi Pranata
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35	Health Communication in the Media (Study of Published Literature in 2020-2025)	<p>This study design is based on the growing complexity of health communication issues in Indonesia, particularly the information gap among various stakeholders. Health communication traditionally covers scientific information exchange, communication within healthcare teams, practitioner–patient interactions, institutional communication, and the dissemination of health information through mass media. Today, this scope has expanded to include social media engagement and the use of e-health applications. Challenges arising from public engagement on social media highlight the need for better reality construction in addressing health problems. Through a literature review of studies published between 2020–2025, this research will apply concepts from the science communication model, particularly citizen science and open science. These frameworks emphasize active public involvement, open data access, and shared responsibility among researchers, practitioners, and the public. This approach is expected to offer a more inclusive and collaborative foundation for improving health communication in Indonesia.</p>	health; communication; media; literature	Lidwina Mutia Sadasri; Rajiyem Rajiyem; Y.A. Nunung Prajarto
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36	Redaction Management of the Dialogue Program of <i>Sorot Prestasi</i> at RRI Surakarta in the Context of the Media and Digital Transformation	<p>This study examines the redaction management of the Dialog Program <i>Sorot Prestasi</i> at RRI Surakarta amid ongoing media and digital transformation. Advances in digital technology have changed editorial workflows from planning to distribution, creating challenges for RRI to stay relevant in a competitive digital landscape. The study analyses redaction strategies and the team's ability to adapt to technological change and shifting audience behaviour. Using a descriptive qualitative case study, data were collected through interviews, production observations, and documentation review. The findings show that redaction management has shifted toward a collaborative, technology-based workflow. Digital platforms such as RRI Play Go, YouTube, and social media successfully expand audience reach and engagement. However, gaps remain in staff digital skills and maintaining consistent cross-platform content distribution. The study concludes that effective redaction management in the digital era requires synergy between technological innovation, human resource capacity, and institutional support to develop an adaptive and responsive multiplatform news production model.</p>	Redaction Management; RRI Surakarta; Digital Transformation; Media Production; Multiplatform Broadcasting	Dwi K Relawati
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37	Threat Modelling Analysis Using STRIDE for Secure Forensic Report Sharing	<p>Secure collaboration in digital forensic investigations requires mechanisms that guarantee report confidentiality and integrity. Traditional centralized methods are vulnerable to tampering and unauthorized access. To overcome this, ShareBlock was developed as a private blockchain system using Hyperledger Fabric and IPFS to provide decentralized, verifiable, and auditable forensic report sharing. However, its overall security posture has not been fully assessed. This study conducts a comprehensive threat modelling analysis of ShareBlock using the STRIDE framework. Based on the system architecture, potential threats are identified across spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service, and privilege escalation. Each threat is evaluated by likelihood and impact to produce a risk matrix and corresponding mitigation strategies. The results show that while ShareBlock already applies pre-upload encryption, role-based access control, and blockchain-based integrity protection, weaknesses remain in signature verification processes and privilege isolation. This analysis strengthens ShareBlock's security design and demonstrates the value of STRIDE in developing more resilient blockchain-based forensic collaboration systems.</p>	Blockchain; Hyperledger Fabric; IPFS; Digital Forensics; Threat Modelling; STRIDE	Risna Purwita Siwi; Yudi Prayudi; Niken Cahyani
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38	Strategic Adaptability in the Digital Era: Mapping Research on Digital Leadership and Dynamic Capabilities (2019-2025)	<p>The acceleration of digital transformation since 2019 has reshaped organizational leadership and capability-building practices. This study maps the intellectual structure, thematic evolution, and emerging trends linking digital leadership and dynamic capabilities. A total of 218 Scopus-indexed publications (2019–2025) were analysed using Biblioshiny, enabling descriptive, conceptual, and intellectual structure analyses. Results show a strong rise in publications after 2020, reflecting greater recognition of digital leadership as a strategic enabler of dynamic capabilities. Co-citation and keyword analyses identify three main clusters: digital leadership driving sensing, seizing, and transforming activities; mediating mechanisms such as innovation, agility, and digital culture; and sustainability-oriented capability development. Emerging themes include AI-enabled leadership, ecosystem adaptability, and green digital transformation. The study contributes by framing digital leadership as a microfoundation of dynamic capabilities, bridging behavioral and strategic management theories. Practically, it provides insights for policymakers and business leaders to strengthen adaptability, innovation, and sustainability through leadership-driven digital transformation.</p>	digital leadership; dynamic capabilities; bibliometric analysis; innovation	Rieka Mustika; Ade Sobandi; Cut Zellatifanny
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39	<p>Artificial Intelligence Literacy for Elementary School Teachers: A Case Study in Magelang Regency</p>	<p>This study analyzes the level of AI literacy among elementary school teachers in preparing for the 2025/2026 Coding and Artificial Intelligence Curriculum (KKA). Using Long and Magerko's (2020) AI Literacy Framework—covering what AI is, what it can do, how it works, and how to live and work with AI—and Bloom's Taxonomy, the research assesses teachers' conceptual and cognitive mastery of AI-based learning. A quantitative approach with descriptive analysis and multiple linear regression was applied to data from 68 teachers in 10 elementary schools in Magelang Regency. Results show that teachers' AI literacy is moderately high (mean = 3.62), with strong performance in remember (3.91) and understand (3.84), but weaker in apply and create. Regression results indicate that attitudes toward AI ($\beta = 0.497$), education level ($\beta = 0.689$), and AI training experience ($\beta = 0.570$) significantly increase AI literacy. These findings show that teacher readiness for the KKA curriculum requires not only technical skills but also positive attitudes, ethical awareness, and strong conceptual understanding of AI. The study recommends continuous professional development based on Bloom's Taxonomy to enhance teachers' ability to understand, apply, and create AI-aligned learning designs.</p>	<p>Artificial Intelligence; Literacy; Bloom's Taxonomy; Elementary School Teachers; KKA Curriculum</p>	<p>Diyah Ayu Karunianingsih; Yolanda Presiana Desi; Ardian Setio Utomo; Fatikha Akfini Anantaputri</p>
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40	<p>From Framework to Practice: Integrating the 4Cs Online Risk Model and Operational Digital Security Components in First-Year Digital Literacy Education</p>	<p>This study examines how the 4Cs online risk framework, which includes Content, Contact, Conduct, and Commerce or Contract, can be integrated with four operational digital security components, namely privacy protection, content ethics, device security, and critical literacy, to improve digital literacy among first year university students. Early implementation is important because it shapes students' basic digital behavior during their initial academic adaptation. Using a case based learning approach, student groups analyzed real digital safety cases and produced infographics as awareness tools. The findings show that students were able to apply the risk framework in practical actions, develop ethical reflection, and communicate safety messages effectively. Their digital safety awareness improved noticeably. The study's novelty lies in combining the 4Cs framework with a competence-based model aligned with DigComp 2.2, creating a practical and replicable learning design. This approach supports recent research promoting contextual and creative digital literacy. Overall, the model helps cultivate ethical, privacy aware digital citizens and strengthens digital resilience in higher education.</p>	<p>Digital Literacy; Digital Safety; Online Risk; Higher Education; Digital Awareness</p>	<p>Kautsarina Kautsarina; Yolanda Presiana Desi; Fahrizal Lukman Budiono</p>
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41	<p>Enhancing Motivation or Distracting Focus? Exploring the Impact of Digital Gamification Tools on Learner Engagement and Motivation of Undergraduate Students in Uzbekistan EFL Classrooms</p>	<p>In Uzbekistan, educators still face challenges in using digital gamification effectively, especially since classroom phone bans are often overlooked for learning purposes. This study investigates whether digital games such as Quizizz, Kahoot, and Jeopardy increase learners' interest and motivation or instead distract them and reduce critical thinking. Using both qualitative and quantitative methods, the research involved 68 undergraduate students and 21 teachers from the Foreign Languages Faculty of Bukhara State University. Data from questionnaires, observations, and interviews show that collaborative digital games enhance classroom motivation and emotional engagement. Only a small number of teachers expressed concerns about reduced critical thinking. Despite issues such as poor Internet access and low digital literacy among rural students, integrating creative digital media in game form improves student motivation and participation. The study concludes that teachers need continuous professional development to use modern digital tools effectively for educational purposes.</p>	<p>Digital games; EFL; motivation; Quizizz; Kahoot; Jeopardy</p>	<p>Gulnora Abdullaeva</p>
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42	<p>Increasing Motivation or Distracting Focus? Exploring the Impact of Digital Gamification Tools on Learner Engagement and Motivation of Undergraduate Students in Uzbekistan EFL Classrooms</p>	<p>In Uzbekistan, educators still struggle to use digital gamification effectively, even though classroom phone bans are often overlooked for learning activities. This study examines whether digital games such as Quizizz, Kahoot, and Jeopardy increase students' interest and motivation or distract them from core content. Using both qualitative and quantitative methods, the research involved 68 undergraduate students and 21 teachers from the Foreign Languages Faculty of Bukhara State University. Data from questionnaires, observations, and interviews show that collaborative digital games significantly enhance motivation and emotional engagement. Only a small number of teachers expressed concerns about reduced critical thinking. Despite challenges such as weak Internet access and low digital literacy among rural learners, the use of creative digital media in game form improves participation during lessons. The study concludes that continuous professional development is essential to help teachers use modern digital tools effectively in education.</p>	<p>Digital games; motivation; participation; EFL; Kahoot; Quizizz</p>	<p>Gulnora Abdullaeva</p>
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43	<p>Digital Service Innovation Towards Inclusive Public Transport for Persons with Disabilities in Indonesia</p>	<p>This study examines how digital innovation supports inclusive public transport for persons with disabilities in Indonesia across Jakarta, Bandung, Semarang, and Yogyakarta. Using a qualitative descriptive approach with policy review and field interviews, the research evaluates the alignment between digital transformation and accessibility regulations. Findings show that although regulations guarantee equal mobility rights, implementation remains uneven. Jakarta demonstrates the most advanced integration, while other cities face budget limits, low awareness, and limited training. Accessibility in vehicles, terminals, and infrastructure such as ramps, tactile paths, and digital assistive features is inconsistent. Priority seating, emergency buttons, and staff assistance are also not uniformly available. Digital apps frequently lack screen reader support and real-time accessible navigation. These gaps indicate fragmented enforcement and weak digital inclusivity. Strengthening digital platforms, adaptive interfaces, and accessible information systems is essential. The study concludes that future mobility innovation requires a unified accessibility framework, stronger coordination, and wider adoption of assistive technologies to achieve equitable digital mobility.</p>	<p>Digital innovation; Public transport; Inclusive mobility; Accessibility; Persons with disabilities</p>	<p>Tristania Pangaribuan; Oktolina Simatupang</p>
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44	<p>Technical Analysis, Impact, and National Cybersecurity Lessons from the Brain Cipher Ransomware Attack on PDNS 2 Surabaya</p>	<p>The June 2024 Brain Cipher ransomware attack on Indonesia’s National Data Centre (PDNS 2) exposed a major failure in protecting critical digital infrastructure. The LockBit 3.0 variant crippled over 200 public services and pushed digital sovereignty to the centre of national security concerns. This paper provides a technical analysis, impact assessment, and policy review using a qualitative case study and Digital Forensics Review based on official reports and indicators of compromise. The assessment confirms the scale of the crisis: 282 government institutions were affected, disrupting essential services such as immigration and taxation. Technical findings show that attackers exploited remote access points for widespread data encryption. Recovery relied on AWS migration and Batam-based backups, revealing dependence on external infrastructure. The key conclusion is that the PDNS 2 incident proves digital sovereignty is tightly linked to territorial sovereignty. Recommendations include building geographically redundant infrastructure, enforcing automated failover testing, and strengthening behaviour-based detection. Strategically, Indonesia must improve its cybersecurity culture through large scale capacity building to ensure lasting national cyber resilience.</p>	<p>Brain Cipher; Ransomware Attack; PDNS 2; National Cybersecurity; Digital Sovereignty; Impact Assessment, Cyber Resilience, Strategic Mitigation.</p>	<p>Rahmat Rian Hidayat; Yoyok Darmanto; Rahmat Rian Hidayat</p>
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45	Strategic Positioning and Competitive Advantage: A Comparative Analysis of Foreign Media in Indonesia's Digital Landscape	<p>In the era of information globalization, foreign media operating within a country can shape international public perception and influence political dynamics. This study analyses the sources of competitive advantage and strategic positioning of foreign media in Indonesia's digital ecosystem. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research examined 34 registered foreign media outlets from January to March 2025, focusing on ownership, country of origin, digital performance, and audience activation based on the Media Engagement Continuum. The analysis identifies four strategic archetypes: Global Distributors, Regional Engagers, Niche Activators, and Passive Observers. Outlets such as The Straits Times, Channel News Asia, and Al Jazeera achieve sustainable advantage through multiplatform production and active community engagement, while traditional agencies like Reuters and AFP maintain large audiences but show lower participatory engagement. The findings indicate that competitive advantage depends not only on resources but also on digital adaptability and activation strength. This research contributes to Global Media studies by highlighting dynamic, participatory strategies among foreign media operating in developing regions.</p>	strategic management; competitive advantage; digital capabilities; media engagement; Indonesia	Dimas Aditya Nugraha; Alfira Sofia; Atef Fahrudin
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46	Soft Set Theory in Association Rules: From Concept to Integration and Applications	<p>Association Rules Mining (ARM) is useful for finding co-occurrence patterns, yet its classical Boolean model struggles with uncertainty, multi-valued attributes, hierarchies, and temporal changes. Soft set theory offers a simple, parameter-based framework for uncertainty that complements ARM without relying on fuzzy or rough set assumptions. This review shows how soft sets enhance ARM in four ways: reducing dimensionality through soft-set attribute selection, redefining support and confidence to handle noisy or incomplete data, enabling multi-level ARM through multi-soft representations for hierarchical concepts, and using temporal soft sets to capture seasonal or shifting patterns in time-stamped data. Across retail, text mining, IoT streams, and decision-support tasks, these integrations improve rule compactness, coverage, and clarity. Remaining challenges include scalable computation for large soft representations, hybrid models combining fuzzy and soft methods, standardized evaluation metrics, and reproducible toolchains. Overall, soft sets broaden ARM's applicability while preserving its intuitive if-then semantics.</p>	Soft Sets; Association Rules Mining; Fuzzy Soft Sets; Temporal Soft Sets; Integration Soft Sets Association Rules	Zahra Arwananing Tyas; Mustafa Mat Deris; Iwan Riyadi Yanto
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47	The Impact of SBERT Encoder and Indexer Selection on Semantic Search Quality and Efficiency	As information retrieval increasingly adopts semantic search, this study evaluates how combinations of Sentence-BERT encoders and Approximate Nearest Neighbour indexers influence accuracy and efficiency. Using 11 SBERT models and three ANN indexers (FAISS, HNSWLib, Annoy) on 40,000 book catalogue entries, performance was assessed through intrinsic vector metrics, extrinsic retrieval scores (nDCG, MRR), and efficiency (build time, search latency). Findings show that retrieval accuracy is determined solely by the SBERT encoder, with all indexers producing identical accuracy. Intrinsic and practical quality do not always align: sentence-t5-base performs best theoretically, but paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2 yields the highest retrieval accuracy (nDCG 0.9697). FAISS is the most efficient indexer, with the fastest build and search times, while HNSWLib is the slowest. The study concludes that encoder choice governs accuracy, while indexer selection should consider system scale and speed requirements. The optimal combination is paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2 with FAISS.	Semantic Search; Sentence-BERT (SBERT); Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN); Vector Embedding; FAISS; Performance Evaluation	Hafidha Arfiah; Abd Rahim Rahman; Safa Safiera; Tody Ariefianto Wibowo; Sri Astuti
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48	Design and Development of a Security and Door Control System with Monitoring for a Server Room Based on Android	<p>The server room is a vital asset that must be protected not only through physical security but also by maintaining stable environmental conditions, especially temperature, to prevent hardware failure. This study designs and implements an IoT-based security, door control, and monitoring system that integrates multiple protection layers. The system features RFID-based door access control and remote monitoring through an Android application called SIKOMORU. Development used Arduino IDE for microcontroller programming, Android Studio with Kotlin for mobile app development, and Firebase as a real-time database. The hardware consists of an ESP32 microcontroller, DS18B20 temperature sensor, MFRC522 RFID reader for access authentication, Reed Switch for door status detection, and a relay module for controlling the electromagnetic solenoid lock. SIKOMORU enables authorized users to remotely unlock doors and monitor room and server temperatures in real time. The system records access logs and sends notifications for unauthorized attempts, strengthening security oversight. This integrated solution is suitable for educational institutions, corporate offices, and data centres requiring reliable physical security and continuous environmental monitoring.</p>	Server Room; IoT; Firebase; Monitoring; Security; Android Application	Mochamad Alfian Rosid; Galuh Reqa Adji
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49	An Analytical Study on the Implementation of Game-Based Learning Through Interactive Narrative in a Pixel-Art Life Simulation Game: A Case Study of "Citampi Stories"	<p>This study examines the implementation of game-based learning integrated with interactive narrative in the pixel-art life simulation game <i>Citampi Stories</i>. Using a qualitative descriptive method with an exploratory case study approach, data were collected through developer interviews, gameplay observation, and player testing with 20 participants aged 17–25. Thematic analysis with source triangulation ensured data validity. The findings show that the combination of narrative structure, gameplay mechanics, and pixel-art aesthetics significantly enhances emotional and cognitive engagement. Most players experienced strong immersion, better conceptual understanding, and reflective learning related to financial literacy and social interaction. Based on these results, the study proposes a conceptual framework for interactive narrative design in game-based learning, highlighting the importance of local cultural context, branching storylines, and the expressive role of pixel art. The study concludes that <i>Citampi Stories</i> has strong potential as a contextual learning tool in vocational education and offers theoretical insights and practical guidance for local game developers seeking to integrate narrative-driven learning into digital education.</p>	game-based learning; interactive narrative; pixel art; vocational education	R.M Joko Priyono; Sigit Winarso; RB Hendri Kuswanto; Willhelmus Filianto
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50	Inventory Information System and Monitoring of Laboratory Equipment Using QR Code Website-Based	<p>Laboratories are essential to education and research, requiring proper facility and asset management. At the Informatics Study Program, Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, seven laboratories with varied hardware and software face challenges in managing equipment inventory. This study develops a QR Code and website-based Inventory and Monitoring System to improve asset management, reduce loss, and support maintenance decisions. Built using the Extreme Programming method with PHP and CodeIgniter 4, the system integrates QR Code recognition for efficient asset identification. The system streamlines inventory processes, enhances monitoring, and increases maintenance responsiveness. QR Code integration improves equipment traceability, while the website interface provides easy access to asset data, maintenance schedules, and real-time tracking. This solution supports effective laboratory asset management and offers scalable, user-friendly features suitable for broader adoption in educational institutions. Overall, the system shows significant improvements in asset monitoring and contributes to better maintenance and asset longevity.</p>	UMSIDA; Inventory; Monitoring; QR Code; Website	Yunianita Rahmawati; Mochammad Luthfan Hakim
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51	Web-Based Neighborhood Association Financial Information System	<p>The rapid development of information and communication technology has improved efficiency in many sectors, including financial management in community organizations such as Rukun Tetangga (RT). However, RT financial management still faces issues such as time-consuming manual recording, limited transparency, difficulty tracking payment history, and inefficient cash-based transactions. This study develops a web-based financial information system to support online RT fee payments and streamline administrative processes. The system is built using CodeIgniter 4 with a MySQL database, offering features such as automated fee recording, real-time financial reports, payment history tracking, and integration with a secure online payment gateway. Development follows the Extreme Programming (XP) methodology to enable flexible and iterative improvements. The resulting system is expected to enhance operational efficiency, increase financial transparency, provide residents with 24/7 payment access, and modernize overall RT financial management practices.</p>	Information Technology; RT Financial System; Online Payment; CodeIgniter 4; Payment Gateway; Financial Transparency	Mochamad Alfian Rosid; Muhammad Zidny Ilhami
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52	Implementation of the K-Means Algorithm for Clustering the KBIH Jabal Nur Hajj Pilgrim Area	<p>KBIH Jabal Nur is a hajj and umrah guidance institution under the Muhammadiyah Regional Board of Sidoarjo. As registrants increase each year, the institution faces challenges in managing pilgrim data, which affects marketing efficiency and strategy development. This study aims to classify the regions of registered pilgrims to support analysis and decision-making. Using the K-Means clustering method, origin regions were grouped into two categories: areas with the highest number of pilgrims and areas with the lowest. The Elbow Method determined the optimal cluster value, resulting in $k = 2$. Cluster 1 represents the area with the most pilgrims (1,261 data points), all from Sidoarjo Regency. Cluster 0 includes regions with fewer registrants, such as Surabaya, Pasuruan, Mojokerto, Lamongan, Blitar, and Jember. This clustering produces valuable insights for improving data management, optimizing promotional activities, and designing more effective marketing strategies tailored to each region. The findings also suggest targeted outreach and resource allocation to strengthen engagement and increase registrations in underrepresented areas.</p>	KMeans; Clustering; Hajj Pilgrims; KBIH; Regional Promotion; Elbow Method	Deva Martha Shella; Ade Eviyanti
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53	Development of Automatic Vacuum Cleaner Robot With Lidar and Gyroscope Sensors	<p>Cleanliness is an effort made by individuals to create a comfortable and healthy environment. But often getting older and busy sometimes results in cleanliness that is often underestimated and becomes a source of disease. Therefore we need a tool that can certainly help humans in maintaining the cleanliness of the house. This study aims to create an automatic vacuum cleaner robot. This robot is equipped with intelligence when mapping the areas to be cleaned. The lidar sensor in this robot will measure the mapped distance and then the robot will walk down the room until it finds a dirty source and the robot will clean the dirty spots which are detected by the dust sensor. This robot uses a gy521 mpu-6050 gyroscope sensor so that the robot can walk straight and stably with an improved yaw angle. All systems in this robot are controlled by the NodeMCU ESP32 microcontroller which is equipped with Bluetooth which can later support the operation of the robot using a smartphone via the Bluetooth line. It is hoped that in this thesis a good automatic cleaning and tracking vacuum will be created so that it can be used to facilitate work in terms of cleanliness. The results of this study have been successful in making a vacuum robot that can clean dirt and track space with an effectiveness of 75%.</p>	gyroscope, lidar, NodeMCU ESP32, robot, vacuum	Abas Bagas Pramudita Do Kader ¹ , Syamsudduh a Syahririni ^{1a} , Arief Wisaksono ¹ , Shazana Dhiya Ayuni ¹ , Sobirov Bobur Baxtishodovich ²
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54	Monitoring of Ammonia Levels and IoT-Based Aerator Control in Catfish	<p>Water quality is a crucial aspect of fish farming, and one of the waste products generated in catfish farming is ammonia. Ammonia originates from the metabolic waste of fish, such as dissolved feces and unconsumed food, which accumulates at the bottom of the pond. This research aims to develop an ammonia monitoring device using the MQ-135 gas sensor as its primary component. The monitoring device consists of a sensor module and an Android application powered by Blynk. When ammonia levels exceed a certain threshold, it triggers alerts or warnings indicating poor water conditions, and the aerator is activated to increase oxygen levels in the water, thereby reducing dissolved ammonia. Conversely, if ammonia levels drop too low, the Blynk module sends notifications to a mobile device via the Blynk application.</p>	Ammonia, Blynk, Catfish, MQ-135	Adella Hadi Agus TiningVyas ¹ , Shazana Dhiya Ayuni ^{1a} , Agus Hayatal Falah ¹ , R. Dwi Hadidjaja Rasjid Saputra ¹ , Gaziyevev Alisher Nematovich ²
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55	Telegram-Based Control System for Monitoring Oyster Mushroom Conditions	<p>Oyster mushroom is a mushroom that has many benefits and is popular with the public. The oyster mushroom cultivation process requires temperature and humidity in the mushroom house every time so farmers have to check the temperature and humidity directly. A tool is needed to monitor and control the temperature and humidity of the mushroom house based on the Internet of Things using Telegram. The design of this tool uses the DHT-11, ESP32 Cam and Nodemcu sensors. DHT-11 sensor to monitor room temperature and humidity. The results of sensor readings can be found via Telegram Bot by sending a request message. Humidifiers and mini portable air conditioners are used as prototypes to control humidity and temperature in the cultivation room. In this system, an experiment was carried out on the accuracy of the DHT11 sensor compared to the HTC monitoring tool, for monitoring other parameters it will be material for development in further research. By implementing the design and monitoring of temperature and humidity in the oyster mushroom barn, it can help and increase the efficiency level of farmers in obtaining optimal oyster mushroom yields.</p>	AC Mini Portable, ESP32 Cam, Humidifier, Internet of Things, NodeMCU ESP8266, Oyster Mushroom, Telegram	Andi Putra Pamungkas ¹ , Dwi Hadidjaja Rasjid Saputra ^{1a} , Agus Hayatal Falah ¹ , Shazana Dhiya Ayuni ¹ , Sulaymanov Israel Isomiddinovich ²
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56	Digital Resilience of Economic Ecosystems: A Bibliometric Analysis in Biblioshiny	<p>This paper explores the concept of digital resilience within economic ecosystems, proposing a novel framework grounded in bibliometric analysis using the Biblioshiny platform. Drawing from a dataset of documents sourced from the Lens database as of September 24, 2023, the study identifies key drivers influencing the emergence and development of digital resilience in economic systems. The thematic mapping reveals emerging clusters of research, revealing significant growth in studies focusing on digital resilience and the ecosystem approach. The findings offer policymakers, researchers, and managers a comprehensive understanding of how digital resilience functions across various economic sectors. The study highlights the importance of systems thinking and adaptability, predicting a transformation in cross-disciplinary research and practical applications in developing robust, adaptable digital economic ecosystems.</p>	Digital Resilience; Economic Ecosystems; Bibliometric Analysis; Biblioshiny; Data-driven Insights	Yulia Vertakova; Elena Shkarupeta; Vladimir Avidskiy; Natalia Brovko
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57	<p>The Need to Implement an Intelligent Knowledge Management System in the Companies of the Railway Industry of Kazakhstan for Effective Management of Investment Projects</p>	<p>The article highlights the importance of implementing an intelligent knowledge management system in companies within the railway industry of Kazakhstan to ensure efficient management of investment projects. It discusses the need for innovative approaches to improve project efficiency, reduce risks, and enhance decision-making processes. The study emphasizes that modern knowledge management platforms can significantly support the development and execution of investment projects. It also analyzes factors influencing project success, including organizational capacity, human resources, and technological readiness. The authors argue that introducing intelligent knowledge management tools can optimize information flow, strengthen project coordination, and improve the overall effectiveness and quality of investment project management. The research provides practical recommendations for implementing such systems and highlights the necessity for strategic reforms to strengthen Kazakhstan's railway sector.</p>	<p>Investment Project; Knowledge Management; Intellectual Platform; Corporate Education System; Intellectual Capital</p>	<p>Alashbayeva Nursulu; Turekulova Dametken; Lukpanova Zhanar; Kulyash Baigabulova; Sugir Dinara</p>
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58	Current Trends in Digital Financial Technologies	<p>In recent years, digital financial technologies have become an integral part of the banking sector, transforming traditional models of customer service and business operations. The article analyzes trends in the development of financial technologies in the context of digitalization. Foreign experience in the development and implementation of advanced technologies, including artificial intelligence, modes of seamless integration of payment and credit services, BNPL services, banking chatbots, etc., is examined. The main attention is paid to assessing the impact of these technologies on the efficiency of banking operations, improving the quality of customer service, and increasing the security level of financial transactions. The main provisions of the Concept of Artificial Intelligence Development of Kazakhstan for 2024–2029 were studied. The results of the analysis show the crucial importance of maintaining the leading role of AI-based financial technologies in regulatory processes and customer data protection. The paper provides a comparative analysis of the most popular digital services and shows their further development in the context of globalization and technological progress. The conclusions indicate that banks must adapt to new technological realities in order to maintain competitiveness and ensure sustainable growth.</p>	Digital Technology; Fintech; Artificial Intelligence; Concept; Banks; Finance	Tomiris Mussilimova ; Serik Makysh; Gulzhan Alina; Dinara; K. Kerimkulova
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59	IoT-Based Temperature and Humidity Control for Oyster Mushroom Cultivation	<p>Oyster mushroom is a plant that can be cultivated in Indonesia. One of the important factors in mushroom cultivation is temperature and humidity. A good temperature for the growth of oyster mushrooms is 20–30°C. Good humidity for the growth of oyster mushrooms is >80%. Maintaining the temperature and humidity is generally still done manually by sprinkling water into the kumbung room periodically. In an effort to make the mushroom farmer's job easier, a tool was created that can maintain the temperature and humidity of the mushroom house with an IoT-based data logger. Temperature and humidity values are measured using a DHT22 sensor. NodeMCU V3 is used to control and send temperature and humidity data to the Web Google Sheets. The test was carried out for 15 days with a temperature set point <30°C and humidity >80%. The results of this study are that the tool can maintain a temperature of 23–30.2°C and humidity of 78–100%. Google Sheets web is used to record temperature and humidity data. Data can be downloaded in (.XLSX) format and can be analyzed using a line chart.</p>	data logger, DHT22, google sheets, internet of things, NodeMCU V3	Ahmad Ansori ¹ , Shazana Dhiya Ayuni ^{1a} , Agus Hayatal Falah ¹ , Akhmad Ahfas ¹ , Ravshanov Normahmad Kayumovich ²
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60	Protecting Against Hidden Cyber Threats in a Cloud-Based Learning Environment of a University	<p>The paper shows that the threat of breach of access to confidential information can be prevented in a cloud-based learning environment (CLE) of a university, generating a comprehensive method to detect hidden cyber threats (SW) propagation and to develop an algorithm for identifying these threats for the CLE of a university. The method aims to protect the university's information environment from cyberattacks, including rootkit technologies that allow attackers to hide their activity within the operating system or memory. The approach offers guaranteed detection of hidden threats and improves the protection of the learning environment by providing rapid threat identification and appropriate mitigation measures. The method further contributes to providing a secure CLE, thereby ensuring the safety and confidentiality of university data.</p>	cloud-based environment; university; hidden cyber threats; rootkit technologies	Bereke Madina; Lakhno Valerii; Dametken Turekulova; Zhilkishbayeva Gulnaz
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